

B1MG Stakeholder Meeting Agenda Wednesday, 17th November 2021

Meeting Location Details:

B1MG Stakeholder Meeting. 10:00 -17:00 CET (09:00 - 16:00 GMT) connection opens at 09:30 CET

Goal: Gain stakeholder feedback and recommendations across all use cases on elements of the 1+MG Trust Framework

Today's [minutes](#)

Location: Virtual meeting - Please note that this meeting will be recorded

Dial-in details:

<https://elixir-europe-org.zoom.us/j/85274955482?pwd=c1N2ZVlp1bmU1ZE9jTlI0dktNaUJTZz09>

Meeting ID: 852 7495 5482

Passcode: 485337

Support contact: B1MG-Coordination@elixir-europe.org

Note: The times in the agenda are **CET**

9:30 10:00	Arrival & registration (waiting room open for virtual participants)
10:00	Welcome (Serena Scollen)
10:05 11:00	<p>Introduction to the Trust Framework (Chairs: Ruben Kok & Serena Scollen)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• ELSI aspects of the Trust Framework: Regina Becker• Data standards and data quality aspects: Jeroen Belien• Infrastructure aspects: Tommi Nyronen <p>Discussion</p> <p>Go to www.menti.com from your phone or computer and enter the code OR scan the QR Code to start participating in today's meeting polls.</p> <p>6558 7815</p>

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11:00 11:15	Coffee Break
11:15 12:15	<p>Presentation from the European Commission: Szymon Bielecki, DG CNECT</p> <p>“Public trust and engagement: challenges for genomics and its implementation in health care” Carla van El, Department of Human Genetics, AmsterdamUMC, NL</p> <p>Discussion</p> <p>General introduction to the afternoon programme</p>
12:15 13:00	Lunch break
13:00 14:45	<p>Use case workshops (per disease area, workshops in parallel)</p> <p>GOAL: list of recommendations to thematic WGs/WPs from use case perspective to be discussed adopted in the work processes of these WP's</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rare Diseases (WG8) Chairs: Marco Tartaglia & Sergi Beltran <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERN-ITHACA and the Rare Disease landscape in Europe (Klea Vyshka, Robert Debré University Hospital, Paris, FR) • The Screen4Care EU-IMI project: aims and vision (Alessandra Ferlini, S.Anna University Hospital & University of Ferrara, Ferrara, IT) • Solve-RD (Lisenka Vissers, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, NL) • GenoMed4ALL (Federico Álvarez, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, ES) • EJP RD (Annalisa Landi, Fondazione per la Ricerca Farmacologica Gianni Benzi Onlus, Bari, IT) • Cancer (WG9) Chairs: Giovanni Tonon & Nina Habermann <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GHGA - Jan Korbel (EMBL, Heidelberg) • EUCANCan/ICGC-ARGO - David Torrents, (BSC, Barcelona) • Common and complex diseases (WG10) Chairs: Andres Metspalu & Serena Scollen <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The FinnGen-study - Mervi Aavikko (University of Helsinki) • PerMed project in Estonia: delivering genomics based health care - Lili Milani (UTARTU) • Synthetic genome data simulation project - Tero Hiekkalinna (National Institute of Health and Welfare, Finland) • Infectious Diseases (WG11) Chairs: Katja Kivinen & Emanuela Oldoni <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The COVID-19 Data Portal - Guy Cochrane (EMBL-EBI) • ISIDORE project - Romain David (ERINHA) • BY-COVID project - Katharina Lauer (ELIXIR Hub) • EC COVID-19 workshop series - Lauren Maxwell (Heidelberg Institute for Global Health) • Industry (WG7) Chairs: Silja Elunurm & Merlijn van Rijswijk <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perspective of the Estonian Biobank why Industry Involvement is crucial and a introduction to the work of the Industry involvement working group - Silja Elunurm

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	<p>(Estonian Ministry of Social Affairs, WG 7 1+MG)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Genomics as part of the health research puzzle: industry view - Danny van Roijen (Digital Health Director, Cocir) • Personalized Healthcare why data skills are crucial to get there - Wendy Maas (Policy Lead Personalised Healthcare, Roche The Netherlands) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Genome of Europe (WG12) Chairs: André Uitterlinden & Ruben Kok <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WG12 status update - André Uitterlinden (Erasmus MC)
14:45 15:00	Wrap-up from workshops
15:00 15:15	Coffee Break
15:15- 15:45	Report from the workshops WGLs (5 mins per presentation)
15:45 -16:15	General Discussion on the outcomes of the workshops and recommendations on the Trust Framework
16:15 16:30	Wrap-up with the WPLs of the morning session (Ruben Kok & Serena Scollen)
16:30	Meeting ends